

Studies on Organic Sulfur Compounds as Emulsifying Agents

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Thiourea, thioacetamide, ammonium thiocyanate and phenothiazine which are listed as good fungicides in literature have been tried as emulsion stabilisers. The effect of addition of a few previously studied gums on the stability of emulsions stabilised by these organic sulphur compounds has also been studied applying the size frequency analysis of King and Mukerjee. It is concluded that single organic sulfur compounds are not capable of producing good and stable emulsions. Addition of Indian gums improves the stability coefficients and nature of the oil also plays an important role so far as the stability and the specific areas of the emulsions produced are concerned.

IN continuation with the previous work on arsenicals¹⁵, copper compounds¹⁶, D.D.T.¹⁷ and Bordeaux mixtures¹⁸ of different types the work has been further extended to the study of a few organic sulphur compounds.

Phenothiazine, thiodiphenylamine, introduced as an insecticide in 1935, may be considered one of the early members of the newer synthetic age. This compound has been reported as highly toxic to a number of insects, including mosquito larvae, aphids, codling moth and Mexican bean beetle^{5,8,9}. Fungicidal value of phenothiazine has been noted by Goldsworthy and Green against apple scabs, venturia inaequalis¹⁴.

Thioacetamide (CH_3CSNH_2) is effective in reducing the decay in oranges caused by stem end rot and blue and green molds from about 40% to 2% or less¹¹. It gives average control of the flesh fly larva, *Lucilia sericata*.

Thiocyanates include some of the earliest recognised effective insecticides used against aphids, mealy bugs and spider mites^{6,7}. Wilcoxon and Hartzell published a series of papers^{2,10} showing results from the use of various thiocyanates against aphids, and mealy bugs, *Pseudococcus* Sp; smaller European elm bark beetle, *Scolytus multistriatus*, potato flea beetle, *Epitrix cucumeris* and spidermite, *Tetranychus telarius*.

Ammonium thiocyanate is used generally as a herbicide but with greater success on annuals than on perennials. The results are generally not as permanent as those from sodium arsenite and borex⁴.

Thiourea (NH_2CSNH_2) is toxic to fresh fly larva, *Lucilia sericata*. It is also very effective against the house fly larva. A number of related compounds, including ethyl, methyl, propyl, butyl and amyl thiourea were effective against the flesh fly larva but at slightly higher concentrations than that of thiourea alone¹. It is equally effective to thioacetamide against decay of oranges¹¹. In the present work it is intended to study the above mentioned organic sulphur compounds as emulsion

stabilisers which have been listed as good and representative insecticides and fungicides. The effect of addition of a few previously studied gums on the stability coefficients of these fungicides has also been studied.

Experimental

The gums were purified by the methods as described by Mukherjee and Shukla¹² in their earlier work on gums. The emulsions were prepared at 30° by King and Mukherjee's² method using fixed concentration of the sulphur compounds alone and then by adding fixed amounts of gums keeping the ratio of the oil (kerosene or olive) to water as 30 : 70 so that the emulsions produced were not very viscous and could be sprayed easily for practical purposes. The size frequency analysis was done immediately and on regular intervals of time on specific surfaces of these emulsions applying the theory of least squares as described by Mukherjee and Shukla^{12,13}.

Results and Discussion

A comparison of the data of size frequency analysis (table 1), in case of thioacetamide in combination with 0.1% Bel gum stabilized emulsions of kerosene and olive oils, reveals that although in emulsion no. 121 the finer particles of sizes 1μ - 4μ were absent from the very beginning of preparation of emulsion and the percentage of 5μ particles was also low (89.18%), the dispersion varied from 89.18% (5μ) to 0.28% (25μ) on the first day, but the emulsion particles remained fine even after 2 months storage time as can be seen from the distribution of particles of various sizes.

On the other hand with the same system in case of olive oil emulsion some particles of sizes ranging between 1μ - 4μ were present from the very beginning of preparation and particles of 5μ size were as high as 97.24%. A few particles of 2μ to 4μ sizes were present even after 6 weeks storage time. Rapid deterioration of the emulsion took place in this case

TABLE I—PERCENTAGE DISTRIBUTION OF OIL DROPLETS OF DIFFERENT SIZES IN HOMOGENISED EMULSIONS.
(INDICES OVER THE EMULSION NO. DENOTE THE NUMBER OF WEEKS THAT HAVE ELAPSED)

Mean diameter (μ)	Emulsion no. \rightarrow	121 ⁰	121 ¹	121 ²	121 ³	121 ⁴	121 ⁶	121 ⁸	121 ⁸	134 ⁰	134 ⁷	134 ¹	134 ³	134 ⁴	134 ⁵	134 ⁸
1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.61	—	—	—	—	—	—
2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.99	1.81	1.75	1.57	1.13	1.25	1.20
3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.68	1.45	1.64	1.69	1.68	1.19	1.00
4	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.36	0.45	0.66	0.75	0.55	0.99	0.90
5	89.18	86.55	76.86	75.90	72.50	—	72.23	70.77	97.24	94.93	93.48	91.42	90.65	79.87	50.50	34.74
10	8.11	9.81	14.35	15.00	15.30	—	16.62	15.92	0.12	0.94	1.44	3.15	3.61	9.48	19.00	27.51
15	1.53	2.18	3.15	3.20	3.67	—	3.75	4.77	—	0.27	0.57	0.75	1.13	6.98	14.00	18.34
20	0.90	1.52	2.31	2.40	2.65	—	3.22	3.66	—	0.15	0.33	0.48	0.90	4.49	9.00	13.02
25	0.28	0.94	1.85	1.90	2.04	—	2.14	3.18	—	—	—	0.13	0.19	0.45	3.20	3.32
30	—	—	0.83	0.90	1.02	—	1.18	1.27	—	—	—	—	—	0.50	1.20	2.57
35	—	—	0.65	0.70	0.82	—	0.86	0.95	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
40	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.48	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Free Oil separation p.c	(nil)	(0.25)	(0.5)	(0.5)	(0.5)	—	(1.0)	(1.5)	(all)	(2.5)	(11.5)	(13.5)	(15.0)	(20.)	(24.0)	(28.0)
Agent																

0.5% Thioacetamide + 0.1% Bel Gum
(Olive Oil Emulsion)

0.5% Thioacetamide + 0.1% Bel Gum
(Kerosene Oil Emulsion)

as can be seen from the percentage of the particles of different sizes and this was due to rapid coarsening of the particles which took place with the ageing of the emulsion.

Stability: In table 2, the data on stability coefficients and specific areas have been collected. From this data it can be seen that :

In case of kerosene oil as internal phase no emulsions were possible with either of the three organic sulphur compounds.

However combination of Dhak gum with thioacetamide produced most stable emulsion with stability coefficient as 53.87. The least stable emulsion was obtained in case of ammonium thiocyanate with stability coefficient equal to 21.09.

Nature of Oil: With the above mentioned organic sulphur compounds as stabilisers the stability of an emulsion seems to vary considerably with the nature of oil. This variation is rather specific with different agents and also with combinations of these agents with gums.

Except in case of ammonium thiocyanate, somewhat stable emulsions were produced with all other single organic sulphur compounds.

In case of gum combinations with these agents (olive oil as internal phase) definite trends are obtained so far as the changes in stabilities and initial specific area values are concerned. Stability coefficients in all the systems follow the same order : Dhak gum > Bel gum > original single substance > katira gum.

TABLE 2—DATA FOR 30% KEROSENE OIL AND OLIVE OIL EMULSIONS

Emulsion no.	Gums	Kerosene Oil			Emulsion no.	Olive Oil		
		Initial Specific Area $\times 10^3$		Stability coefficient $K \times 10^3$		Initial Specific Area $\times 10^3$		Stability coefficient $K \times 10^3$
		Calculated	Graphically determined			Calculated	Graphically determined	
<i>0.5% Thiourea Stabilised Emulsions</i>								
115.	Only thiourea	—	—	Broken	128	9.89	10.00	1.58
116.	+0.1% Dhak gum	14.77	11.22	30.83	129	6.03	5.75	32.61
117.	+0.1% Bel gum	7.95	6.31	39.84	130	13.42	11.75	11.35
118.	+0.1% Katira gum	7.56	7.24	0.89	131	—	—	Broken
<i>0.5% Thioacetamide stabilised Emulsions</i>								
119.	Only thioacetamide	—	—	Broken	132	7.46	7.41	1.30
120.	+0.1% Dhak gum	14.78	10.47	53.87	133.	6.76	6.45	45.92
121.	+0.1% Bel gum	8.25	5.89	41.93	134.	13.81	11.48	11.90
122.	+0.1% Katira gum	—	—	Broken	135.	—	—	Broken
<i>0.5% Ammonium thiocyanate stabilised Emulsions</i>								
123.	Only Ammonium thiocyanate	—	—	Broken	136.	—	—	Broken
124.	+0.1% Dhak gum	5.49	4.48	21.09	137.	2.97	2.95	84.53
125.	+0.1% Bel gum	15.18	15.14	126.20	138.	13.82	13.49	69.39
126.	+0.1% Katira Gum	—	—	Broken	139.	—	—	Broken
<i>0.5% Phenothiazine stabilised Emulsions</i>								
127.	Only Phenothiazine	—	—	Broken	140.	—	—	Broken

Note.—Emulsions of Phenothiazine with combinations of gums were also broken immediately after preparation.

Ammonium thiocyanate emulsions in cases of different gum combinations showed a behaviour similar to those of thiourea in combinations with different gums as can be seen from the table 2.

Calculated initial interfacial area values and graphically determined initial interfacial area values showed a similar trend in case of different agents when used in combination with different gums.

Katira gum proved to be detrimental as emulsions were not possible with thioacetamide and ammonium thiocyanate. Very unstable emulsion was possible only in case of thiourea.

Practically determined initial specific area values and graphically determined ones also show a similar gradation. The order of decrease of these interfacial areas can be represented as follows :

Bel gum > sulphur compound alone > Dhak gum > Katira gum. Once more Katira gum proved to be detrimental in all the three cases of sulphur compounds.

In general kerosene oil emulsions were found to be finer in comparison to the olive oil emulsions as can be seen from the size frequency analysis data as well as from the initial specific area values collected in table 2.

From the above discussion it can be concluded that single organic sulphur compounds are not capable of producing stable emulsions. Addition of Indian gums improves the stability coefficients probably due to greater adsorption of these gums at the interface and formation of viscous and tough film preventing the coalescence of the oil droplets.

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